

Research article

Global linear modeling of AFM indentation curves for soft samples with various indenter geometries

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ABSTRACT

Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) is a critical technique for probing the mechanical properties of biological and soft materials at the nanoscale, offering high spatial resolution and sensitivity under near-physiological conditions. In biomedical contexts, especially oncology, quantifying cell and tissue stiffness via nanoindentation with Young's modulus as a key parameter provides essential diagnostic insights. However, the interpretation of force-indentation data remains constrained by the complexity of classical contact mechanics models, particularly for non-ideal indenter geometries such as sphero-conical tips or deep spherical indentations. As a result, over-simplified models like Hertz and Sneddon are often used beyond their ideal regimes. To overcome these limitations, we introduce a unified linearization framework that enables geometry-independent analysis of AFM nanoindentation data. By combining the general nanoindentation differential equation with the weighted mean value theorem for integrals, we derive simplified analytical expressions that allow Young's modulus to be extracted via straightforward linear fitting. This method is compatible with spherical, parabolic, conical, and sphero-conical indenters, eliminating the need for geometry-specific nonlinear fitting procedures. Unlike conventional methods, the proposed approach allows each indentation curve to be analyzed with the most appropriate contact model, determined by its maximum indentation depth, using linear fitting and a simple correction factor for different indenter geometries, thereby enabling accurate mapping of Young's modulus. Validation against both simulated and experimental data, from fibroblasts and agarose gels, demonstrates excellent agreement with classical models while significantly streamlining data analysis. This framework paves the way for faster, more accessible, and broadly applicable mechanical characterization of soft materials using AFM, with potential to enhance diagnostic and materials discovery workflows in biomedical and soft-matter research.

1. Introduction

Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) has become an essential technique for determining the mechanical properties of biological materials at the nanoscale, primarily due to its capability to perform measurements in conditions that closely mimic the physiological environment [1,2]. Its remarkable resolution at the sub-nanometer level, coupled with sensitivity to forces in the pico-newton range, allows researchers to detect nanoscale structural changes and compositional variations, as well as to observe dynamic intercellular interactions within complex biological networks during disease progression [3–5]. A number of pioneering

studies have demonstrated AFM's potential as a nano-diagnostic modality, offering objective and quantitative indicators to evaluate pathological states, most notably by distinguishing healthy from diseased tissues [6]. Additionally, AFM facilitates the minimally invasive visualization of nanoscale architectures, mechanical behavior, and even single-molecule events within cellular and tissue contexts [7].

In medical research, AFM has found widespread application, particularly in oncology. One of its most significant contributions lies in identifying differences in mechanical stiffness between normal and cancerous cells, with Young's modulus serving as a key diagnostic marker [8–17]. Measuring stiffness enables discrimination between

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malignant and non-malignant cells, thereby offering a label-free and quantitative approach to cancer diagnosis [8]. The effectiveness of AFM in oncological diagnostics has been validated through studies involving normal, benign, and malignant tissue samples [18–23]. Notably, Plodinec et al. reported that while normal and benign human breast tissues show uniform stiffness profiles, malignant tissues exhibit bimodal stiffness distributions [18]. Beyond cancer, AFM has also proven valuable in diagnosing other pathological conditions, such as osteoarthritis [24,25] and Alzheimer's disease [26–29], among various additional disorders [30].

AFM-based nanoindentation is widely recognized as a principal technique for quantifying the nanoscale mechanical behavior of biological specimens, particularly in biomedical research aimed at disease diagnosis [30,31]. The interpretation of force-indentation curves generated during these experiments relies on mathematical modeling, with the choice of models depending on factors such as indenter geometry and indentation velocity [32–38]. Indentation testing enables in situ, microscale, and non-destructive characterization of materials, offering significant practical benefits. It has been extensively applied not only to determine the Young's modulus of a wide range of materials, including metals [39,40], hyperelastic materials [41,42], and biomimetic materials [43,44], but also to calibrate elastic-plastic properties [45,46] and to probe local mechanical heterogeneities at the micro- and nanoscale [47,48]. The versatility of indentation further allows the study of thin films, coatings, and small or otherwise challenging samples, establishing it as a standard tool across materials science, biomechanics, and nanotechnology.

For soft biological tissues examined at low indentation speeds using spherical indenters, the Hertzian contact model is most frequently applied to fit the experimental data. Under these conditions, the relationship between the applied force F and the indentation depth h is described by the following equation [32]:

$$F = \frac{4}{3} \frac{E}{1-\nu^2} R^{1/2} h^{3/2} \quad (1)$$

In Eq. (1), F represents the force exerted on the material, h denotes the indentation depth, E and ν correspond to the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the material, respectively, and R is the radius of the indenter. The validity of this model relies on the assumption that the indentation depth remains much smaller than the indenter's radius ($h \ll R$) [49]. For large indentation depths, Sneddon's equations should be used instead:

$$F = \frac{E}{2(1-\nu^2)} \left[(r_c^2 + R^2) \ln \left(\frac{R+r_c}{R-r_c} \right) - 2r_c R \right] \quad (2)$$

where r_c is the contact radius between the indenter and the sample. The following equation links the indentation depth to the contact radius and the tip radius [50,51]:

$$\ln \left(\frac{R+r_c}{R-r_c} \right) = \frac{2h}{r_c} \quad (3)$$

However, Eqs. (2) and (3) do not offer a direct relationship between the applied force and the indentation depth. To simplify data processing, Müller et al. [52] proposed an alternative approach based on Eq. (1), incorporating a polynomial correction:

$$F = \frac{4}{3} \frac{E}{1-\nu^2} R^{1/2} h^{3/2} \left[1 - \frac{1}{10} \left(\frac{h}{R} \right) - \frac{1}{840} \left(\frac{h}{R} \right)^2 + \frac{11}{15120} \left(\frac{h}{R} \right)^3 + \frac{1357}{6652800} \left(\frac{h}{R} \right)^4 \right] \quad (4)$$

An alternative equation, derived using the generic nanoindentation differential equation and numerical methods, was presented by Kontomaris and Malamou to provide accurate results for very large indentation depths (as $h/R \rightarrow \infty$) [50,53]:

$$F = \frac{4ER^{\frac{1}{2}}}{3(1-\nu^2)} h^{\frac{3}{2}} Z \quad (5)$$

where,

$$Z = c_1 + \sum_{M=2}^N \frac{3}{2M} c_M R^{\left(\frac{3}{2}-M\right)} h^{M-\frac{3}{2}} \quad (6)$$

The coefficients c_1, c_2, \dots, c_M and the number of terms in Eq. (6) depend on the h/R ratio. For very large indentation depths, six terms should be used, and the appropriate coefficients are presented as follows: $c_1 = 1.0100000$, $c_2 = -0.0730300$, $c_3 = -0.1357000$, $c_4 = 0.0359800$, $c_5 = -0.0040240$ and $c_6 = 0.0001653$ [50].

To further simplify data processing, Kontomaris et al. [54] derived a simpler equation based on a power-law form similar to Eq. (1). The aim was to find a straightforward power-law expression that results in the same work done by the indenter (i.e., the same area under the force-indentation curve) and the same indentation depth [54]:

$$F = a \frac{E}{1-\nu^2} R^{2-m} h^m \quad (7)$$

For $h/R \leq 1.32$, $a = 1.191$ and $m = 1.397$ [54]. In addition, in many cases, pyramidal indenters are used in AFM indentation experiments and are typically approximated as perfect cones [18,32]:

$$F = \frac{2}{\pi} \frac{E}{1-\nu^2} \tan(\theta) h^2 \quad (8)$$

In Eq. (8), θ is the cone's half-angle. For the case of a symmetric 4-sided pyramid the coefficient $2/\pi$ in Eq. (8) should be replaced with $1/\sqrt{2}$ [55]. However, for shallow indentations, the indenter is more accurately approximated as sphero-conical. This is a significantly more complicated case. The applied force is related to the contact radius between the indenter and the sample as follows [56]:

$$F = \frac{2E}{1-\nu^2} \left\{ r_c h - \frac{r_c^2}{2 \tan(\theta)} \left[\frac{\pi}{2} - \arcsin \left(\frac{R_T}{r_c} \right) \right] - \frac{r_c^3}{3R} + (r_c^2 - R_T^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[\frac{R_T}{2 \tan(\theta)} + \frac{r_c^2 - R_T^2}{3R} \right] \right\} \quad (9)$$

where R_T is the transition radius between the spherical and the conical parts of the indenter and $r_c > R_T$. For $r_c < R_T$, Eq. (1) should be used instead of Eq. (9) [56]. The indentation depth (for $r_c > R_T$) is related with the contact radius with the following equation [56]:

$$h = \frac{r_c}{\tan(\theta)} \left[\frac{\pi}{2} - \arcsin \left(\frac{R_T}{r_c} \right) \right] - \frac{r_c}{R} \left[(r_c^2 - R_T^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} - r_c \right] \quad (10)$$

When the spherical tip merges smoothly (i.e., tangentially) with the conical body of the indenter, the transition radius between the spherical and conical sections is given by [56]:

$$R_T = R \cos(\theta) \quad (11)$$

Since Eqs. (9) and (10) are not straightforward to use in the fitting process, a new equation for sphero-conical indentations has been recently derived [57]:

$$F = \frac{2}{\pi} \frac{E}{1-\nu^2} \tan(\theta) h^2 + \frac{4}{\pi} \frac{E}{1-\nu^2} (R_T - \tan(\theta) h_T) h \quad (12)$$

where, h_T is the transition depth between the spherical and the conical parts of the indenter. The cases discussed above cover nearly all scenarios commonly used in the literature for deriving Young's modulus in purely elastic contact. Fig. 1 presents the classic cases of parabolic (Fig. 1

Fig. 1. Classic cases of parabolic (a), spherical (b), conical (c), and sphero-conical (d) indenters.

(a)), spherical (Fig. 1(b)), conical (Fig. 1(c)), and sphero-conical (Fig. 1(d)) indenters.

It is evident that the complexity of the fitting process depends on the geometry of the indenter and the assumptions made by the user (e.g., conical or sphero-conical contact). It is important to note that, despite the availability of appropriate analytical models for nearly all cases, Eqs. (1) and (8) are still widely used by the majority of the AFM community when testing soft biological samples. Although these classical models, Eq. (1) for a paraboloid indenter and Eq. (8) for a perfectly conical tip, yield reliable results under specific conditions, they are based on idealized geometries. In more realistic or complex scenarios, such as the use of spherical indenters at large indentation depths or sphero-conical tips that combine multiple geometric features, more advanced analytical or numerical formulations are necessary to account for nonlinearities and the geometric complexity of the contact. However, these sophisticated models often involve complex mathematical expressions and require iterative fitting procedures, as discussed above, which can limit their practical use in routine AFM data analysis.

The aim of this paper is to simplify the fitting process in all cases by introducing a novel linearization method for force-indentation data on soft biological samples. In other words, we present a unified, geometry-independent fitting procedure, accompanied by simple analytical expressions, for determining Young's modulus from nanoindentation data using a linear fitting approach. In contrast to conventional methods, the proposed approach enables the analysis of each indentation curve using the most suitable contact model, determined by its maximum indentation depth, without requiring prior assumptions about the tip-sample geometry. This enables accurate mapping of Young's modulus in heterogeneous samples.

This paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 (Materials and Methods), a linearization method applicable to any indenter geometry, based on the general differential equation for axisymmetric indenters

and the weighted mean value theorem for integrals, is introduced. In Section 3 (Results), the new approach is applied to parabolic, spherical, conical, and sphero-conical indenters. Additionally, both simulated force-indentation data and experimental data from fibroblasts and agarose gels are analyzed using classical equations and the proposed linear method, yielding nearly equivalent results. Section 4 (Discussion) summarizes and interprets the results, highlighting the advantages of the proposed approach.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Streamlining data processing

Consider the general nanoindentation differential equation [58]:

$$\frac{dF}{dh} = 2E^*r_c(h) \quad (13)$$

where $r_c(h)$ represents the contact radius between the indenter and the sample at the contact depth. In addition, E^* is the reduced modulus ($E^* = E/(1 - \nu^2)$). Eq. (13) can be rewritten as the product of two functions, f and g , where f depends on the indentation depth and g depends solely on the indenter's properties:

$$\frac{dF}{dh} = 2E^*f(h)g(i) \quad (14)$$

In other words, $r_c(h) = f(h)g(i)$. In Equation (14), i denotes a parameter related to the geometry of the indenter. Solving this differential equation and considering $F = 0$ at $h = 0$, we obtain:

$$F = 2E^* \int_0^h f(y)g(i)dy \quad (15)$$

To proceed from Eq. (15), the weighted mean value theorem for integrals is applied [59]. It is important to note once again that $g(i)$ is independent of the integration variable y . Since f is continuous on $[0, h]$, and $g(i)$ is constant, hence integrable and of constant sign, the theorem applies, and there exists a point $c \in (0, h)$ such that [59]:

$$\int_0^h f(y)g(i)dy = f(c) \int_0^h g(i)dy = f(c)g(i)h \quad (16)$$

Substituting Eq. (16) into Eq. (15), we obtain the simplified linear form:

$$F = 2E^*f(c) \int_0^h g(i)dh = 2E^*f(c)g(i)h \quad (17)$$

This expression highlights a linear dependence of the applied force F on the indentation depth h , where the nonlinearity is absorbed into the value of f evaluated at some intermediate point $c \in (0, h)$. The next step is to calculate the $f(c)$ value. Let us consider the work done by the indenter (using the actual force – indentation function $F(h)$) in the domain $0 \leq h \leq h_{\max}$:

$$W = \int_0^{h_{\max}} F(h)dh \quad (18)$$

In addition, using the linearized Eq. (17):

$$W = \int_0^{h_{\max}} 2E^*f(c)g(i)h dh = E^*f(c)g(i)h_{\max}^2 \quad (19)$$

By combining Eqs. (18) and (19) it is concluded:

$$f(c) = \frac{\int_0^{h_{\max}} F(h)dh}{E^*g(i)h_{\max}^2} \quad (20)$$

Thus, using Eq. (20), Eq. (17) is written as below:

$$F = 2 \frac{\int_0^{h_{\max}} F(h)dh}{h_{\max}^2} h \quad (21)$$

or,

$$F = \lambda h \quad (22)$$

where,

$$\lambda = 2 \frac{\int_0^{h_{\max}} F(h)dh}{h_{\max}^2} = 2E^*f(c)g(i) \quad (23)$$

At this point, it is important to emphasize that the procedure presented above is based on an ‘equivalent’ linear curve having the same indentation depth and the same area under the curve as the real curve. However, most software packages perform linear fitting using the least-squares method. In a classic linear fitting approach, the slope of the fit is calculated as follows:

$$\lambda' = \frac{\int_0^{h_{\max}} hF(h)dh}{\int_0^{h_{\max}} h^2 dh} \quad (24)$$

It is evident that Eq. (23) differs from Eq. (24). Therefore, a systematic error will arise if Eq. (23) is used for Young’s modulus calculations with a simple linear fit performed by conventional software packages. To eliminate this error, the following correction factor is introduced:

$$\Omega = \frac{\lambda'}{\lambda} \quad (25)$$

Finally, the correct Young’s modulus is calculated using the following equation:

$$2E^*f(c)g(i)\Omega = \lambda' \Rightarrow E = \frac{\lambda'(1 - \nu^2)}{2f(c)g(i)\Omega} \quad (26)$$

The correction factor Ω and the parameters $f(c)$ and $g(i)$ depend on the indenter’s geometry and will be calculated for parabolic, spherical, conical and sphero-conical indenters in Section 3 (Results Section).

2.2. Open access simulated data

This study utilized open-access simulated data representing an elastic half-space with a Young’s modulus of $E = 20\text{kPa}$ and a Poisson’s ratio of $\nu = 0.5$. The data were generated in Mathematica 8.0 using spherical and spheroconical indenters. The cantilever’s spring constant was 0.1N/m in all cases [60]. The radius of the spherical indenter was $1\mu\text{m}$, while the radii of the sphero-conical indenters were $0.1\mu\text{m}$ and $0.2\mu\text{m}$, with a cone half-angle of 35° . Synthetic data were created using the aforementioned indenters, with random Gaussian noise added [60]. The simulated force–indentation data were retrieved from the AtomicJ repository [60]. Young’s modulus was determined using the classic fitting procedures in AtomicJ software, as well as the linear fitting approach proposed in this paper.

2.3. Open access experimental data from fibroblasts

Open-access nanoindentation data obtained using a conical indenter on human fibroblasts were employed in this study [60]. As reported in [60], human fibroblasts were cultured and maintained at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5 % CO_2 . An AFM tip (Veeco Probes) with a nominal tip radius of 20nm , a half-angle of 25° , and a spring constant of 0.01N/m was used for the measurements [60]. The experimental force–indentation data on fibroblasts were retrieved from the AtomicJ repository [60]. Young’s modulus was determined using the classic equations with AtomicJ software, as well as by the method proposed in this paper.

2.4. AFM experiments on agarose gels

Measurements were carried out using colloidal AFM probes (CP-PNPL-BSG-A, sQube; obtained from NanoAndMore GMBH) equipped with spheres of nominal radius $1\mu\text{m}$. Prior to experimentation, the indenters were calibrated using the AFM test grating TGT1 (NT-MDT Instruments). The experiments utilized agarose gels at a concentration of 2.5 % placed in 35 mm petri dishes. Owing to their high-water content, a Poisson’s ratio of $\nu = 0.5$ was assumed. The determination of Young’s modulus for the agarose gels was performed using the AtomicJ software and the linear fitting approach proposed in this paper.

2.5. FEA modelling

To numerically simulate the problem of nanoindentation of an elastic half-space we consider the axisymmetric geometry shown in Fig. 2, where r denotes the radial (polar) axis and z the vertical one. The computational domain comprises of two non-overlapping regions, namely Ω_i and Ω_s , where Ω_i represents an indenter having a spherical tip with radius R , whereas Ω_s the elastic half-space (specimen). In addition,

Fig. 2. The axisymmetric geometry used for numerical simulation of the problem.

let W be the width and H the height of the specimen, respectively. To ensure that simulation results are free of finite-size effects, the values of W and H have to be chosen to be large with respect to R (i.e. $W \gg R$ and $H \gg R$). Based on the results presented in [61], letting $W = H = 10R$ guarantees that the results are independent of the size of the specimen.

To simulate the problem of penetration of the elastic half-space, at the bottom boundary of Ω_s a fixed support (i.e. zero-displacement, zero-rotation) boundary condition is imposed. The right boundary of Ω_s is left unconstrained. A uniformly distributed downward force of magnitude F is applied at the top boundary of S_i , as shown in Fig. 2. The contact between the indenter and the specimen was modeled using the augmented Lagrange method, which yielded excellent results [61]. On Ω_i and Ω_s a linear elastic material was assigned by specifying Poisson's ratio and Young's modulus. To ensure that Ω_s acts as a rigid body we set $E_i \gg E_s$ in all cases. Regarding Poisson's ratio, in all cases presented hereafter we set $\nu_i = 0.2$ and $\nu_s = 0.5$. The computational domain was meshed utilizing quadrilateral elements of size 5×10^{-8} m which was found in our previous publication [61] to result in mesh-independent results. The numerical simulations were conducted in ANSYS Academic Mechanical 2025 R2 software.

3. Results

3.1. Parabolic and spherical indenters ($i = R$)

The first case to be examined is that of perfect parabolic indenters. In this case, the geometry-related parameter (i) is indenter's radius, R . To apply the newly proposed linearization method presented in Section 2.1, we consider the following function:

$$g(R) = R^{1/2} \quad (27)$$

Using Eqs. (1), (20), (23) and (24) the $f(c)$, λ , λ' parameters are easily determined:

$$f(c) = \frac{\int_0^{h_{\max}} \frac{4}{3} E^* R^{1/2} h^{3/2} dh}{E^* R^{1/2} h_{\max}^2} = \frac{8}{15} h_{\max}^{1/2} \quad (28)$$

$$\lambda = 2 \frac{\int_0^{h_{\max}} \frac{4}{3} E^* R^{1/2} h^{3/2} dh}{h_{\max}^2} = \frac{16}{15} E^* R^{1/2} h_{\max}^{1/2} \quad (29)$$

$$\lambda' = \frac{\int_0^{h_{\max}} \frac{4}{3} E^* R^{1/2} h^{5/2} dh}{\int_0^{h_{\max}} h^2 dh} = \frac{8}{7} E^* R^{1/2} h_{\max}^{1/2} \quad (30)$$

Therefore, the correction factor Ω becomes: $\Omega = 15/14$. Thus, equation (26) for parabolic indenters results in:

$$E = \frac{7(1 - \nu^2)}{8R^{1/2} h_{\max}^{1/2}} \lambda' \quad (31)$$

In other words, the proposed method involves performing a linear fit (i.e., $F = \lambda'h$) to the force-indentation data obtained using parabolic indenters in order to determine the slope λ' of the fitted curve. Subsequently, the Young's modulus can be readily calculated using Eq. (31). Eq. (31) is also valid for spherical indentations if $h_{\max} \ll R$ [62,63]. A typical limit in the literature is $h_{\max} < R/10$ [62,63]. For deep spherical indentations, Eqs. (5)-(7) should be used instead of Eq. (1). Based on Eq. (7), the g -function in this case can be defined as follows:

$$g(R) = R^{2-m} \quad (32)$$

Using Eqs. (7), (20), (23) and (24) the $f(c)$, λ , λ' parameters are easily determined:

$$f(c) = \frac{\int_0^{h_{\max}} a E^* R^{2-m} h^m dh}{E^* R^{2-m} h_{\max}^2} = \frac{a}{m+1} h_{\max}^{m-1} \quad (33)$$

$$\lambda = 2 \frac{\int_0^{h_{\max}} a E^* R^{2-m} h^m dh}{h_{\max}^2} = \frac{2a}{m+1} E^* R^{2-m} h_{\max}^{m-1} \quad (34)$$

$$\lambda' = \frac{\int_0^{h_{\max}} a E^* R^{2-m} h^{m+1} dh}{\int_0^{h_{\max}} h^2 dh} = \frac{3a}{m+2} E^* R^{2-m} h_{\max}^{m-1} \quad (35)$$

Therefore, the correction factor Ω becomes: $\Omega = \frac{3(m+1)}{2(m+2)}$. Thus, equation (26) for spherical indenters and deep indentations results in:

$$E = (m+2) \frac{(1 - \nu^2)}{3a R^{2-m} h_{\max}^{m-1}} \lambda' \quad (36)$$

where, $a = 1.191$ and $m = 1.397$ as already mentioned in the Introduction. It is also important to note once again that Eq. (7), and consequently Eq. (36), is valid only for $h_{\max} \leq 1.32$. For larger indentations depths, Eqs. (5), (6) should be used for data processing and

the Ω factor will be depth dependent. Since Eqs. (5), (6) are an extension of classic Hertzian equation (Eq. (1)) we can also consider as the geometry – related parameter the same as for parabolic indenters:

$$g(R) = R^{1/2} \tag{37}$$

However, in this case the $f(y)$ function will also depend on the indenter’s radius. However, this fact does not lead to any limitation of the related analysis. Using Eqs. (5), (6) combined with Eqs. (20), (23) and (24) for the determination of the $f(c)$, λ and λ' parameters we conclude:

$$f(c) = \frac{\int_0^{h_{\max}} \left(\frac{4}{3} E^* c_1 R^{\frac{1}{2}} h^{\frac{3}{2}} + E^* c_2 h^2 + \frac{2}{3} E^* c_3 R^{-1} h^3 + \frac{1}{2} E^* c_4 R^{-2} h^4 + \frac{2}{5} E^* c_5 R^{-3} h^5 + \frac{1}{3} E^* c_6 R^{-4} h^6 \right) dh}{E^* R^{1/2} h_{\max}^2}$$

$$= \frac{\frac{8}{15} c_1 h_{\max}^{\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{1}{3} c_2 R^{-\frac{1}{2}} h_{\max} + \frac{1}{6} c_3 R^{-\frac{3}{2}} h_{\max}^2 + \frac{1}{10} c_4 R^{-\frac{5}{2}} h_{\max}^3 + \frac{1}{15} c_5 R^{-\frac{7}{2}} h_{\max}^4 + \frac{1}{21} c_6 R^{-\frac{9}{2}} h_{\max}^5}{\tag{38}}$$

$$\lambda = 2 \frac{\int_0^{h_{\max}} \left(\frac{4}{3} E^* c_1 R^{\frac{1}{2}} h^{\frac{3}{2}} + E^* c_2 h^2 + \frac{2}{3} E^* c_3 R^{-1} h^3 + \frac{1}{2} E^* c_4 R^{-2} h^4 + \frac{2}{5} E^* c_5 R^{-3} h^5 + \frac{1}{3} E^* c_6 R^{-4} h^6 \right) dh}{h_{\max}^2}$$

$$= E^* \left(\frac{16}{15} c_1 R^{\frac{1}{2}} h_{\max}^{\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{2}{3} c_2 h_{\max} + \frac{1}{3} c_3 R^{-1} h_{\max}^2 + \frac{1}{5} c_4 R^{-2} h_{\max}^3 + \frac{2}{15} c_5 R^{-3} h_{\max}^4 + \frac{2}{21} c_6 R^{-4} h_{\max}^5 \right) \tag{39}$$

$$\lambda' = \frac{\int_0^{h_{\max}} \left(\frac{4}{3} E^* c_1 R^{\frac{1}{2}} h^{\frac{5}{2}} + E^* c_2 h^3 + \frac{2}{3} E^* c_3 R^{-1} h^4 + \frac{1}{2} E^* c_4 R^{-2} h^5 + \frac{2}{5} E^* c_5 R^{-3} h^6 + \frac{1}{3} E^* c_6 R^{-4} h^7 \right) dh}{\int_0^{h_{\max}} h^2 dh}$$

$$= E^* \left(\frac{8}{7} c_1 R^{\frac{1}{2}} h_{\max}^{\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{3}{4} c_2 h_{\max} + \frac{2}{5} c_3 R^{-1} h_{\max}^2 + \frac{1}{4} c_4 R^{-2} h_{\max}^3 + \frac{6}{35} c_5 R^{-3} h_{\max}^4 + \frac{1}{8} c_6 R^{-4} h_{\max}^5 \right) \tag{40}$$

Thus,

$$\Omega = \frac{\frac{8}{7} c_1 R^{\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{3}{4} c_2 h_{\max}^{\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{2}{5} c_3 R^{-1} h_{\max}^{\frac{3}{2}} + \frac{1}{4} c_4 R^{-2} h_{\max}^{\frac{5}{2}} + \frac{6}{35} c_5 R^{-3} h_{\max}^{\frac{7}{2}} + \frac{1}{8} c_6 R^{-4} h_{\max}^{\frac{9}{2}}}{\frac{16}{15} c_1 R^{\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{2}{3} c_2 h_{\max}^{\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{1}{3} c_3 R^{-1} h_{\max}^{\frac{3}{2}} + \frac{1}{5} c_4 R^{-2} h_{\max}^{\frac{5}{2}} + \frac{2}{15} c_5 R^{-3} h_{\max}^{\frac{7}{2}} + \frac{2}{21} c_6 R^{-4} h_{\max}^{\frac{9}{2}}} \tag{41}$$

Finally, the Young’s modulus is calculated using Equation (26). In other words, the proposed method involves performing a linear fit (i.e.,

$F = \lambda' h$) to the force–indentation data obtained using parabolic or spherical indenters in order to determine the slope λ' of the fitted curve. Subsequently, the Young’s modulus can be readily calculated using Eq. (31) for parabolic indenters or Eq. (36) for spherical indentations. Alternatively, equation (26) can be used along with Eqs. (37), (38) and (41).

In Table 1, characteristic values of $f(c)$, λ , λ' and Ω , introduced in Eqs. (38)–(41), are presented for the domain $0 \leq \frac{h_{\max}}{R} \leq 3$. The same values are presented graphically in Fig. 3.

To evaluate the accuracy of the proposed method, classic fitting approaches will be applied to simulated data obtained using spherical indenters, as well as to AFM experimental data on agarose gels, as

described in Sections 2.2 and 2.4. Firstly, Fig. 4 presents six simulated force–indentation curves obtained on an elastic half-space with $E = 20\text{kPa}$, each corresponding to a different indentation depth (the first curve corresponds to $h_{\max} = 0.2R$, while the last one corresponds to

Table 1
The $f(c)$, λ , λ' and Ω values for spherical indentations based on Eqs. (38)-(41).

h_{\max}/R	$f(c)/h_{\max}^{1/2}$	$\lambda/(E^*R)$	$\lambda'/(E^*R)$	Ω
0.1	0.5303	0.3354	0.3590	1.0705
0.5	0.5141	0.7270	0.7763	1.0678
1.0	0.4950	0.9901	1.0536	1.0641
1.5	0.4762	1.1663	1.2364	1.0601
2.0	0.4578	1.2948	1.3673	1.0560
2.5	0.4402	1.3920	1.4645	1.0521
3.0	0.4236	1.4675	1.5385	1.0484

Fig. 3. Spherical indentations (Eqs. (37)-(41)): The $f(c)/h_{\max}^{1/2}$ values (figure a), the $\lambda/(E^*R)$ and $\lambda'/(E^*R)$ values (figure b)) and the Ω values (figure c) with respect to h_{\max}/R in the domain $0.1 \leq h_{\max}/R \leq 3$.

$h_{\max} = 0.9R$). The h_{\max}/R ratio is clearly presented in this case. The slope of the linear curve λ' is also presented in each case. The Young's modulus was calculated using Eq. (36).

The differences from the expected value of 20 kPa were minor and attributed to random Gaussian noise (as explained in Section 2.2), combined with the fact that Eq. (7), which was used to derive Eq. (36), is an approximate but convenient expression for spherical indentations.

The Young's modulus was also calculated using Equation (26), in combination with Eqs. (37), (38), and (41). The results are nearly identical to those obtained using Eq. (36). A comparative presentation of the results calculated using Eq. (36) and those obtained from Eqs. (26), (37), (38), and (41) is provided in Table 2.

In addition, in Fig. 5(a), AFM force – indentation data obtained on an agarose gel (according to the protocol presented in Section 2.4) are presented. The data were first fitted to Sneddon's equations for spherical indenters (Eqs. (2) and (3)) using the AtomicJ software. The Young's modulus resulted in 149 kPa. Subsequently, the method proposed in this paper (i.e., linear fit) was also applied. The Young's modulus in this case resulted equal to 150 kPa. The results are nearly identical. In Fig. 5(b), the data from 20 force-indentation curves processed using the classic Sneddon equations, as well as Eq. (36) based on a simple linear fit, are also presented. The results are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. When using Sneddon's equations $E_{\text{Sn}} = 141.64 \pm 5.19$ kPa while when using the linear fitting $E_{\text{Linear}} = 141.75 \pm 5.62$ kPa. The results prove the accuracy of the proposed approach.

In addition, to further test the proposed method, a simulation process was performed as described in Section 2.5 (Fig. 6). In Fig. 6(a), the sample's Young's modulus was set to 100 kPa, while in Fig. 6(b) it was set to 1000 kPa. In both cases the maximum applied force was $F = 8.54 \times 10^{-8}$ N. In Figs. 6c and 6(d), the data corresponding to the simulations presented in Figs. 6a and 6(b) are shown. For the case of the 100 kPa sample (Figs. 6a and 6c), the data were fitted to Sneddon's equation (since the indentation was deep, $h > 0.5R$) and the linear model proposed in this paper. The resulting Young's modulus was 99.5 kPa using Sneddon's analysis and 101 kPa using the linear method along with Eq. (36). Both results are in excellent agreement with the value of 100 kPa used in the simulation. For the case of the sample with $E = 1$ MPa, Hertz's equation resulted in 1.02 MPa, while the linear method (using Eq. (31), since the maximum indentation depth was significantly smaller than the indenter's radius) gave 1.04 MPa, demonstrating the accuracy of the proposed approach regardless of the stiffness of the tested sample.

3.2. Conical indenters ($i = \theta$)

The first case to be examined is that of perfect conical indenters. In this case, the geometry-related parameter (i) is the cone's half-angle, θ . To apply the newly proposed linearization method presented in Section 2.1, we consider the following function:

$$g(\theta) = \frac{2}{\pi} \tan(\theta) \quad (42)$$

Therefore, the $f(c)$ parameter can be easily calculated using Eq. (20):

$$f(c) = \frac{\int_0^{h_{\max}} \frac{2}{\pi} E^* \tan(\theta) h^2 dh}{E^* \frac{2}{\pi} \tan(\theta) h_{\max}^2} = \frac{1}{3} h_{\max} \quad (43)$$

The λ parameter can be determined using Eq. (23):

$$\lambda = 2 \frac{\int_0^{h_{\max}} \frac{2}{\pi} E^* \tan(\theta) h^2 dh}{h_{\max}^2} = \frac{4}{3\pi} E^* \tan(\theta) h_{\max} \quad (44)$$

The parameter λ' , as obtained from a classic least-squares fitting, is given by:

Fig. 4. Open access, simulated force – indentation data using a spherical indenter with radius $R = 1 \mu\text{m}$ on an elastic half space with $E = 20 \text{kPa}$. The h_{\max}/R ratio, the slope of the linear fit and the calculated Young's modulus is presented in each case.

$$\lambda' = \frac{\int_0^{h_{\max}} \frac{2}{\pi} E^* \tan(\theta) h^3 dh}{\int_0^{h_{\max}} h^2 dh} = \frac{3}{2\pi} E^* \tan(\theta) h_{\max} \quad (45)$$

Therefore, the correction factor Ω becomes: $\Omega = 9/8$. Thus, equation (26) for conical indenters results in:

$$E = \frac{2\pi(1 - \nu^2)}{3 \tan(\theta) h_{\max}} \lambda' \quad (46)$$

In other words, the proposed method involves performing a linear fit (i.e., $F = \lambda' h$) to the force-indentation data obtained using conical indenters in order to determine the slope λ' of the fitted curve. Subsequently, the Young's modulus can be readily calculated using Eq. (46). To evaluate the accuracy of the proposed method we present typical force indentation data obtained on a fibroblast (according to the protocol presented in Section 2.3) in Fig. 7(a).

Using a fit to Eq. (8) we obtain 4.96 kPa. In addition, by performing a linear fitting combined with Eq. (46), we conclude in 5.10 kPa. In Fig. 7 (b) we present the results from 20 force-indentation curves on a fibroblast using a conical indenter. When fitting the data to Eq. (8), $E_{\text{Sn}} = 7.60 \pm 2.27 \text{kPa}$. In addition, when using the linear fitting $E_{\text{Linear}} = 7.89 \pm 2.40 \text{kPa}$.

Although the proposed linearized method is mathematically equivalent to Sneddon's model, small deviations in the extracted elastic modulus were observed when both approaches were applied to fibroblast data. These differences are mainly due to the assumptions of homogeneity, isotropy, and linear elasticity, which do not fully capture the complex mechanical behavior of living cells. Fibroblasts are intrinsically heterogeneous, with mechanical properties strongly influenced by the

Table 2

Young's modulus values for the cases presented in Fig. 4 were calculated using Eq. (36), and subsequently using Eqs. (26), (37), (38), and (41).

h_{\max}/R	E (kPa) (Eq. (36))	E (kPa) (Eqs. (26), (37), (38), (41))
0.2	19.72	20.05
0.4	19.48	20.11
0.6	19.71	20.06
0.7	19.87	20.07
0.8	20.03	20.13
0.9	20.06	20.08

spatial organization of the cytoskeleton, including actin filaments, microtubules, and intermediate filaments, which is non-uniform and anisotropic. Additionally, the finite number and distribution of force-indentation data points, along with experimental noise, can contribute to slight variations in the fitted modulus values. Such discrepancies are therefore expected when approximating a heterogeneous biological system with idealized contact models. Nonetheless, the overall agreement between the two methods supports the robustness of the proposed framework.

3.3. Sphero-conical indenters ($i = \theta$)

In this case, we will use Eq. (12), which is an extension of Eq. (8). The geometry-related parameter can be considered the same as in the case of conical indenters ($i = \theta$), and the same g -function as for perfect conical indenters (Eq. (42)) can be applied. However, in this case the $f(y)$ function will also depend on the indenter's radius and the cone's semi angle. However, this fact does not lead to any limitation of the related analysis. Using Eq. (12) combined with Eqs. (20), (23) and (24) for the determination of the $f(c)$, λ and λ' parameters we conclude:

Fig. 5. Experiments on an agarose gel using a spherical indenter with radius $1\mu\text{m}$. (a) Force – indentation data processed using the classic Sneddon's equations (Eqs. (2) and (3)) and the linear fit proposed in this paper. (b) The results obtained by processing 20 force – indentation curves using Eqs. (2), (3) (Sneddon's Eq.) and using Eq. (36) (linear fit). The results are nearly identical.

$$f(c) = \frac{\int_0^{h_{\max}} \left[\frac{2}{\pi} E^* \tan(\theta) h^2 + \frac{4}{\pi} E^* (R_T - \tan(\theta) h_T) \right] h dh}{E^* \frac{2}{\pi} \tan(\theta) h_{\max}^2} = \frac{1}{3} h_{\max} + \frac{R_T - \tan(\theta) h_T}{\tan(\theta)} \quad (47)$$

The transition depth can be easily calculated as follows [57]:

$$(R - h_T)^2 = R^2 - R_T^2 \Rightarrow R - h_T = R \sqrt{1 - \cos^2(\theta)} \Rightarrow h_T = R(1 - \sin(\theta)) \quad (48)$$

Eq. (47) can be written (using also Eqs. (11) and (48)) as below:

$$f(c) = \frac{1}{3} h_{\max} + R \left[\frac{\cos(\theta)}{\tan(\theta)} + \sin(\theta) - 1 \right] \quad (49)$$

The λ parameter can be determined using Eq. (23):

$$\lambda = 2 \frac{\int_0^{h_{\max}} \left[\frac{2}{\pi} E^* \tan(\theta) h^2 + \frac{4}{\pi} E^* (R_T - \tan(\theta) h_T) \right] h dh}{h_{\max}^2} = \frac{4}{3\pi} E^* \tan(\theta) h_{\max} + \frac{4}{\pi} E^* (R_T - \tan(\theta) h_T) \quad (50)$$

Using Eq. (48), Equation (50) can be written in the following form:

$$\lambda = \frac{4}{3\pi} E^* \tan(\theta) h_{\max} + \frac{4}{\pi} E^* R [\cos(\theta) - \tan(\theta)(1 - \sin(\theta))] \quad (51)$$

The λ' parameter due to a classic least-square fitting should be:

$$\lambda' = \frac{\int_0^{h_{\max}} \left[\frac{2}{\pi} E^* \tan(\theta) h^3 + \frac{4}{\pi} E^* (R_T - \tan(\theta) h_T) \right] h^2 dh}{\int_0^{h_{\max}} h^2 dh} = \frac{3}{2\pi} E^* \tan(\theta) h_{\max} + \frac{4}{\pi} E^* (R_T - \tan(\theta) h_T) = \frac{3}{2\pi} E^* \tan(\theta) h_{\max} + \frac{4}{\pi} E^* R [\cos(\theta) - \tan(\theta)(1 - \sin(\theta))] \quad (52)$$

Therefore,

$$\Omega = \frac{\frac{3}{2} \tan(\theta) + 4[\cos(\theta) - \tan(\theta)(1 - \sin(\theta))] \frac{R}{h_{\max}}}{\frac{4}{3} \tan(\theta) + 4[\cos(\theta) - \tan(\theta)(1 - \sin(\theta))] \frac{R}{h_{\max}}} \quad (53)$$

Finally, the Young's modulus is calculated using Equation (26). In Table 3 we present the $f(c)$, λ , λ' and Ω values for sphero-conical indentations and different R/h_{\max} ratios for $\theta = 25^\circ$. The same variables for $\theta = 35^\circ$ are also presented in Table 4. For $\frac{R}{h_{\max}} \ll 1$, $\Omega \rightarrow 15/14$ (the case of perfect conical indenters). The aforementioned results (i.e., the results presented in Tables 3 and 4) are also graphically presented in Fig. 8.

Fig. 9 presents simulated force-indentation data obtained using sphero-conical indenters with radii of 100 nm (Fig. 9a) and 200 nm (Fig. 9b), and a half-angle of 35° , on an elastic half-space with a Young's modulus of 20 kPa. The data were processed using the method presented in this paper.

In particular, a linear fit was performed and subsequently the $f(c)$ and Ω parameters were calculated using Eqs. (47) and (53). Finally, the Young's modulus was calculated using equation (26) resulting in 20.7 kPa (Fig. 9(a)) and 21.4 kPa (Fig. 9(b)). The minor differences between the accurate value of 20 kPa and the calculated values are due to the random Gaussian noise added to the simulated data to mimic real experimental conditions [60], as well as the fact that Eq. (12) is an approximation for sphero-conical indentations [57].

4. Discussion

Extended research has been conducted to characterize cells and tissues using AFM, employing models that accurately account for indenter geometry and sample dimensions [64–68]. Building on this, recent studies have developed methods to interpret and analyze AFM experimental data more efficiently, aiming to accelerate the process while improving accuracy and reliability. Considerable efforts have also focused on software tools that incorporate advanced contact mechanics models for processing indentation data on soft samples [69]. More recently, machine-learning approaches have been introduced, including artificial neural networks for simulating AFM measurements of elastomer composites, which can continuously improve with new data and efficiently estimate mechanical properties and stress-strain fields at micro- and nanoscale levels [70]. Cutting-edge computational techniques, such as convolutional and recurrent neural networks, are increasingly used to automate the identification of contact points and other key events (e.g., adhesions and indentations), filter low-quality curves, and enable high-throughput, reliable analysis of large AFM datasets [70–73].

In this paper, a new linearization method for any indentation curve was presented, significantly simplifying data processing in AFM nano-indentation experiments on soft samples. Beyond streamlining the

Fig. 6. Deformation of the elastic half-space for two different linear elastic materials for downward applied force $F = 8.54 \times 10^{-8}$ N. Notice that only a portion of the computational domain near the contact region is shown. a) $E_s = 100$ kPa, $\nu_s = 0.5$, b) $E_s = 1000$ kPa, $\nu_s = 0.5$. (Images courtesy of ANSYS Inc.). (c) The force-indentation data were obtained using a simulation process, as described in Section 2.5, for a material with a Young's modulus of 100 kPa. The Young's modulus was calculated using Sneddon's analysis and the proposed linear method, also employing Eq. (36). The results were nearly identical. (d) The simulated force-indentation data for the sample with $E = 1$ MPa. The linear approximation method also led to accurate results in this case.

Fig. 7. Experiments on fibroblasts using a conical indenter. (a) Force-indentation data fitted to the classic Sneddon's equation for conical indenter (Eq. (8)) and the linear fit proposed in this paper. (b) The results obtained by processing 20 force-indentation curves using Eq. (8) (Sneddon's equation for conical indenters) and using Eq. (46) (linear fit). The results are nearly identical.

Table 3

The $f(c)$, λ , λ' , and Ω values for sphero-conical indentations with a cone semi-angle of $\theta = 25^\circ$, based on Eqs. (47)–(53).

$\theta = 25^\circ$				
R/h_{\max}	$f(c)/h_{\max}$	$\lambda/(E' h_{\max})$	$\lambda'/(E' h_{\max})$	Ω
0.1	0.4700	0.2790	0.3038	1.0889
0.2	0.6066	0.3601	0.3849	1.0689
0.3	0.7432	0.4413	0.4660	1.0560
0.4	0.8798	0.5224	0.5471	1.0473
0.5	1.0164	0.6035	0.6282	1.0409
0.6	1.1531	0.6846	0.7093	1.0361
0.7	1.2897	0.7657	0.7904	1.0323
0.8	1.4263	0.8468	0.8716	1.0293
0.9	1.5629	0.9279	0.9527	1.0267
1.0	1.6995	1.0091	1.0338	1.0245

Table 4

The $f(c)$, λ , λ' , and Ω values for sphero-conical indentations with a cone semi-angle of $\theta = 35^\circ$, based on Eqs. (47)–(53).

$\theta = 35^\circ$				
R/h_{\max}	$f(c)/h_{\max}$	$\lambda/(E' h_{\max})$	$\lambda'/(E' h_{\max})$	Ω
0.1	0.4077	0.3635	0.4006	1.1021
0.2	0.4820	0.4297	0.4669	1.0866
0.3	0.5564	0.4960	0.5332	1.0750
0.4	0.6307	0.5623	0.5994	1.0660
0.5	0.7051	0.6286	0.6657	1.0590
0.6	0.7794	0.6949	0.7320	1.0534
0.7	0.8537	0.7611	0.7983	1.0489
0.8	0.9281	0.8274	0.8646	1.0450
0.9	1.0024	0.8937	0.9309	1.0416
1.0	1.0768	0.9600	0.9971	1.0386

analysis, the proposed approach offers a major advantage over traditional fitting methods. In typical AFM experiments, the maximum indentation depth in each curve can vary significantly depending on the local elastic properties of the tested materials. Therefore, the appropriate fitting model for each force curve may differ. Conventional data processing procedures do not account for this variation, leading to significant errors when generating Young's modulus maps. In other words, all curves are typically processed using the same model, regardless of the actual tip-sample contact geometry in each case. For example, while the perfect conical approximation may be valid for some curves, it can result in substantial errors for others. In contrast, the approach proposed in this paper enables the extraction of the slope from the linear fit and the maximum indentation depth without requiring any prior assumption about the contact geometry between the tip and the sample for each individual curve. This allows for rapid data processing using basic tools, along with the application of different equations (i.e., different models) for calculating Young's modulus based on the maximum indentation depth. In other words, the proposed method not only simplifies the initial data processing but also enables the use of multiple contact mechanics models on the same dataset, thereby maximizing accuracy and producing precise Young's modulus maps. A characteristic example is the combination of shallow and deep sphero-conical indentations. For $r_c < R_T$, Eq. (31) should be used for data processing, while for $r_c > R_T$, Equation (26), along with Eqs. (42), (49), and (53), should be used instead. The simplicity of the proposed approach facilitates the development of lightweight software that can be easily integrated into basic analysis tools.

It is important to note that the results presented in Section 3 demonstrate the effectiveness and generality of the proposed linearization method for determining Young's modulus from force-indentation data. This linear fitting approach is applicable to parabolic, spherical, conical and sphero-conical indenters. The generic idea relies on expressing the force-indentation relationship as a linear function, using the general indentation differential equation for axisymmetric indenters

and the weighted mean value theorem for integrals. An appropriate correction factor was also introduced so that the slope λ' can be extracted via straightforward linear regression and subsequently used to estimate the elastic modulus. For parabolic indenters, the theoretical analysis revealed that the correction factor Ω remains constant and equal to 15/14. Additionally the $f(c)$ parameter depends only on the indentation depth. Consequently, the derived expression (Eq. 31) enables a direct calculation of Young's modulus from the linear fit, using only the maximum indentation depth and the indenter radius. Importantly, this expression remains valid for spherical indenters under shallow indentation conditions (typically when $h_{\max} < R/10$), as widely accepted in the literature [62,63]. This highlights the flexibility of the proposed formulation and its compatibility with established Hertzian models.

In contrast, for deeper spherical indentations, an alternative approximate power-law model (Eq. 7) is adopted, from which a more general expression for the elastic modulus (Eq. 36) is derived. The g -function in this case changes to the one presented by Eq. (32), reflecting the different geometric influence under larger deformations. The correction factor Ω , now becomes $\Omega = \frac{3(m+1)}{2(m+2)}$, where $m = 1.397$. Eq. (7) and the approximation of the independence of the Ω -factor from the indentation depth holds for $h_{\max} \leq 1.32R$. For larger indentation depths, Ω is a function of both indentation depth and indenter radius and gradually decreases as the h_{\max}/R ratio increases, as demonstrated in Table 1 and Fig. 3 (which was derived based on Eqs. (5) and (6) that are applicable for any indentation depth). Therefore, for large indentation depths, the most comprehensive formulation is obtained via Eqs. (5), (6), and the corresponding expressions for λ , λ' , and $f(c)$. Equation (26), when used in combination with Eqs. (37), (38), (41), leads to identical results with those obtained via the simplified Eq. (36) (for cases that $h_{\max} \leq 1.32R$), as confirmed by the analysis of simulated data (Table 2). Therefore, in the domain $0 \leq h_{\max}/R \leq 1.32$, the linear fitting method can be applied equally when using Eqs. (5), (6), or (7).

At this point, it is important to highlight that Eq. (7) leads to a constant Ω -value, while Eqs. (5)–(6) result in an Ω -value that depends on both the maximum indentation depth and the indenter's radius (as shown by Eq. (41)) when referring to the exact same domain ($0 \leq h_{\max}/R \leq 1.32$). However, as it is clearly presented in Table 1, the variations of the Ω -parameter in this domain is extremely small. The reason for this 'inconsistency' is that all the aforementioned Eqs. (5)–(7) are approximations of the classic Sneddon's equations for spherical indenters. Eqs. (5)–(6) are more accurate compared to Eq. (7); therefore, they better capture the true nature of the contact between a rigid sphere and an elastic material. On the other hand, Eq. (7) is much easier to use when referring in terms of classic fitting approaches. However, an important conclusion derived from this paper is that both approaches can be easily used in practical applications if the linear fitting approach is used.

The linear fitting method was tested on both simulated and experimental results. When applied to simulated force-indentation data (Fig. 4 and Table 2), the proposed approach yielded accurate calculations of Young's modulus for all tested indentation depths. The calculated Young's modulus remained close to the expected value of 20 kPa, even for relatively deep indentations, with only minor deviations attributable to noise and the approximate nature of Eq. (7). This accuracy was also confirmed by the simulation process shown in Fig. 6. This demonstrates that the linearization technique preserves its reliability regardless the exact value of h_{\max}/R ratio.

When applied to experimental atomic force microscopy (AFM) data obtained from agarose gels, the proposed method again yielded highly satisfactory results. The estimated Young's moduli obtained using the proposed linear fitting were in excellent agreement with those obtained using classic fitting methods. The ability to extract accurate modulus values using a simple linear fit enhances the practical utility of the method in AFM experiments, where data quantity and quality may be limited. In addition, since fitting the force-indentation data to classical

Fig. 8. a) Sphero-conical indentations (Eqs. (49)-(53)) for $\theta = 25^\circ$: The $f(c)/h_{max}$ values (figure i), the $\lambda/(E^*h_{max})$ and $\lambda'/(E^*h_{max})$ values (figure ii) and the Ω values (figure iii) with respect to R/h_{max} in the domain $0.1 \leq R/h_{max} \leq 1$. b) Sphero-conical indentations (Eqs. (49)-(53)) for $\theta = 35^\circ$: The $f(c)/h_{max}$ values (figure i), the $\lambda/(E^*h_{max})$ and $\lambda'/(E^*h_{max})$ values (figure ii) and the Ω values (figure iii) with respect to R/h_{max} in the domain $0.1 \leq R/h_{max} \leq 1$.

equations for deep spherical indentations is not a trivial task, the approach presented in this paper could evolve into a gold standard technique for data processing.

Furthermore, the methodology was extended to conical and sphero-conical indenters [57]. In the case of ideal conical indenters, the linearization approach resulted in straightforward expressions based on the function (42) and again enabled the estimation of Young’s modulus through a linear fit to force–indentation data. The correction factor Ω was found to be equal to 9/8 for ideal cones. Experimental data obtained from fibroblasts, processed using both the classic fitting procedure and the proposed linear approach, yielded nearly identical results.

For sphero-conical indentations, the Ω -factor depends on the indentation depth; however, this does not complicate the analysis since it can be easily calculated using Eq. (53). The $f(c)$ parameter depends on the maximum indentation depth (as in the case of perfect conical indenters) and on the indenter’s geometry, as presented in Eq. (47). In this case as well, the proposed linear fitting led to accurate results.

It is also important to note that the proposed linearization approach is mathematically valid for any value of Young’s modulus, as long as the sample exhibits a linear elastic response. The method relies on transforming the nanoindentation integral into a linear form (Eq. (16)), where $g(i)$ depends only on the indenter geometry and $f(c)$ captures

Fig. 9. Simulated force–indentation data obtained using sphero-conical indenters with radii of 100 nm (Figure a) and 200 nm (Figure b), and a half-angle of 35° , on an elastic half-space with a Young’s modulus of 20 kPa. The slopes of the linear curves, the Ω parameters, and the Young’s moduli calculated using the linear approximation are shown in each case within the graphs.

the indentation depth and indenter shape. The reduced modulus E^* appears in both the integral and the denominator (Eq. (20)), thereby canceling out during the calculation of $f(c)$. The correction factor Ω , used to account for least-squares fitting, is also independent of E^* . Thus, E^* only scales the force without affecting the procedure, similar to classical Hertzian analysis.

Overall, the proposed linearization approach provides a unified and versatile framework for determining Young’s modulus across a wide range of indenter geometries, including parabolic, spherical, conical, and sphero-conical, using a single strategy: a linear fit to the force–indentation curve. The method yields Young’s modulus values that consistently fall within the standard deviation for all tested indenter types, demonstrating its suitability as a simplified and reliable alternative for soft sample measurements. By appropriately selecting the geometry-related function $g(i)$ and correction factor Ω , the method can be systematically adapted to the characteristics of each indenter type.

The proposed linearization methodology for analyzing AFM nano-indentation data addresses key limitations of traditional mechanical characterization techniques. Classical contact mechanics models, such as Hertz and Sneddon, require model-specific, nonlinear fitting procedures that depend on the geometry of the AFM indenter, complicating data analysis and increasing the potential for user error. In contrast, the presented approach introduces a unified, geometry-independent framework, applicable to spherical, parabolic, conical, and sphero-conical tips alike. By converting a traditionally nonlinear process into a simple linear fitting task, this method significantly streamlines data processing, improving computational efficiency and reducing sensitivity to experimental noise. This is particularly advantageous in high-throughput biomedical applications, such as cancer cell stiffness profiling or drug response studies, where rapid and reliable analysis of large datasets is essential. Furthermore, the simplicity of the method

makes it accessible to interdisciplinary research teams, allowing biologists, clinicians, and engineers to extract quantitative mechanical properties without requiring specialized expertise in contact mechanics or curve fitting. Collectively, these features position the approach as a powerful tool for accelerating and standardizing AFM-based mechanical analysis in biomedical research. The results presented here can be readily integrated into existing AFM platforms, providing a clear pathway for broader implementation of the proposed computational approach.

Generic approaches for material characterization have been introduced previously. In particular, the Doerner–Nix method [74] and its later extension by Oliver and Pharr [75,76] provide a widely used framework for determining the elastic modulus of hard materials, where elasto-plastic contact is dominant. These methods rely on analysis of the unloading segment of indentation curves and the concept of an effective indenter, and they have been successfully applied to a broad range of engineering materials. In contrast, AFM indentation of soft biological samples is typically dominated by elastic deformation, and analysis has traditionally been based on Hertz, Sneddon, and related elastic models [8,18,32]. To address this regime, we introduce a linear-fitting procedure that simplifies data processing while remaining applicable across different indenter geometries. This approach provides a robust and efficient alternative for extracting the elastic modulus of soft materials without relying on nonlinear fitting as already mentioned. Although the current study focuses on purely elastic behavior, extending the method to account for more complex responses, such as viscoelasticity, could be an interesting direction for future research.

In addition, the selection of the appropriate model proposed in this paper is based on normalized factors (e.g., h_{\max}/R in spherical indentations). Several studies have introduced normalization approaches to account for the indenter radius (e.g., terms such as h/R). Examples

Table 5

An overview of the proposed method.

An overview of the method
Step 1: We perform a linear fitting to the force – indentation data, $F = \lambda'h$, to determine the slope λ' .
Step 2: We calculate the Young’s modulus using the equations below:
Parabolic indenters (or spherical for $h_{\max} < R/10$): The Young’s modulus is determined using Eq. (31).
Spherical indenters ($0 \leq h_{\max}/R \leq 1.32$): The Young’s modulus is determined using Eq. (36).
Spherical indenters (for any h_{\max}/R ratio): The Young’s modulus is determined using Eqs. (26), (37), (38) and (41).
Conical indenters: The Young’s modulus is determined using Eq. (46).
Sphero-conical indenters: The Young’s modulus is determined using Eqs. (26), (42), (47) and (53).

include corrections of Hertzian equations for finite-thickness samples [77–79], tests on spherical or cylindrical samples incorporating R/R_s (where R_s denotes the sample's radius) [80,81], and analyses of cell mechanics using terms such as s/\sqrt{Rh} , where s is an intrinsic length influenced by surface tension [82]. Other works apply normalization factors in h/R to enable simultaneous approximate determination of both the indenter radius and the sample's Young's modulus [83,84], while some methods use a reference sample to define normalized Young's modulus values independent of the indenter radius [85]. These studies illustrate that normalization is a well-established approach to facilitate meaningful comparisons across different experiments, which is fully considered in the context of our work.

In Table 5, an overview of the proposed method is presented. It is also important to note that the linearization method proposed in this paper, can be applied to other cases as well, such as the classic case of samples with finite thickness. The majority of polynomial corrections found in the literature for samples with finite thickness—regardless of the specific AFM tip geometry or whether the sample is bonded to the substrate—can be expressed in the following general form [77–79]:

$$f(h, H) = 1 + \sum_{n=1}^4 c_n \left[\frac{r(h)}{H} \right]^n \quad (54)$$

where, $r(h)$ is a characteristic length that depends on the indenter's shape (e.g., $r = \sqrt{Rh}$ for parabolic and $r = h \tan(\theta)$ for conical indenters [78,79]). The coefficients c_n depends on both the indenter's properties and on whether the sample is bonded to the substrate.

For example, based on the work of Garcia and Garcia, in the case of conical indenters and cells adhered to the substrate [79]:

$$F = \frac{8}{3\pi} E \tan(\theta) h^2 \left[1 + \frac{0.721 h \tan(\theta)}{H} + \frac{0.650 h^2 \tan^2(\theta)}{H^2} + \frac{0.491 h^3 \tan^3(\theta)}{H^3} + \frac{0.225 h^4 \tan^4(\theta)}{H^4} \right] \quad (54)$$

The linearization method presented in this paper can be easily applied by considering $i = \theta$ and:

$$g(\theta) = \frac{8}{3\pi} \tan(\theta). \quad (55)$$

Subsequently, the Eqs. (20), (23)–(25) can easily lead to the determination of the parameters $f(c), \lambda, \lambda', \Omega$ and finally to the Young's modulus calculation using equation (26).

5. Conclusion

This paper introduces a versatile linearization method for extracting Young's modulus from force-indentation data across various indenter geometries. By reformulating the indentation problem through a linear fitting framework, the method enables accurate modulus estimation using simple regression techniques. The approach accounts for geometric effects through novel equations and correction factors and has been validated against both simulated and experimental AFM data. Its applicability to shallow and deep indentations, along with its ease of implementation, makes it a practical tool for mechanical characterization, particularly in contexts where conventional nonlinear fitting is challenging.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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